

Schotia afra Karoo boer-bean

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 2 m

Distribution:

These endemic trees often occur along the banks of dry streams and small rivers in the Little Karoo, the drier areas of Eastern Cape and the southern part of Western Cape.

Importance:

The Karoo boer-bean serves as both as a shade and ornamental tree. Its leaves are browsed by livestock, and its seeds are edible, consumed green, mature, or roasted and ground into a meal. The bark, when ground and soaked, produces tannin. This versatile tree can be pruned for shaping and is also suitable for bonsai cultivation.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 63.92 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 23.91 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.22 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 88.9%, Duplicated: 10.6%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 91 921 kilobases

Contig number: 864

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Date Published: 2025-12-01

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17736742>

